

GLM P1C1D1B1A1DominiqueP1C1D1B2A2ElisabethP1C1D1B3A3MagaliP1C1D2B1A4Michèle P1C1D2B2A5Jocelyne
P1C1D2B3A6Agnès P1C1D3B1A7ChristianeP1C1D3B2A8MaryseP1C1D3B3A9AnneMarie P1C2D1B1A10Jacqueline
P1C2D1B2A11DanielleP1C2D1B3A12SylvianeP1C2D2B1A13GenevièveP1C2D2B2A14Valérie P1C2D2B3A15Sandrine
P1C2D3B1A16ChristelleP1C2D3B2A17CaroleP1C2D3B3A18StéphanieP2C1D1B1A19Colette P2C1D1B2A20Josette
P2C1D1B3A21LilianeP2C1D2B1A22ElianeP2C1D2B2A23JeannineP2C1D2B3A24Yvette P2C1D3B1A25Gisèle
P2C1D3B2A26DeniseP2C1D3B3A27FrancineP2C2D1B1A28ThérèseP2C2D1B2A29Ghislaine P2C2D1B3A30Delphine
P2C2D2B1A31CélineP2C2D2B2A32CécileP2C2D2B3A33SabineP2C2D3B1A34Sandra P2C2D3B2A35Laure
P2C2D3B3A36Claire
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Behavior 3 Polynomial
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/EMMEANS=TABLES(Drinking.habits COMPARE ADJ(LSD)
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/EMMEANS=TABLES(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)
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/EMMEANS=TABLES(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)
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Physical.activity*Diagnosis Drinking.habits*Diagnosis Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis
Physical.activity*Behavior Drinking.habits*Behavior Physical.activity*D

Drinking.habits*Behavior

Diagnosis*Behavior Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior Drinking.habits
*Diagnosis*Behavior

Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior.

General Linear Model

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Dependent Variable	
1	1	1	1	P1C1D1B1A1 Dominique	
			2	P1C1D1B2A2 Elisabeth	
			3	P1C1D1B3A3 Magali	
	2	1	2	1	P1C1D2B1A4 Michèle
				2	P1C1D2B2A5 Jocelyne
				3	P1C1D2B3A6 Agnès
	3	1	3	1	P1C1D3B1A7 Christiane
				2	P1C1D3B2A8 Maryse
				3	P1C1D3B3A9 AnneMarie
2	1	1	1	P1C2D1B1A1 0Jacqueline	
			2	P1C2D1B2A1 1Danielle	
			3	P1C2D1B3A1 2Sylviane	
	2	1	2	1	P1C2D2B1A1 3Geneviève
				2	P1C2D2B2A1 4Valérie
				3	P1C2D2B3A1 5Sandrine
	3	1	3	1	P1C2D3B1A1 6Christelle
				2	P1C2D3B2A1 7Carole
				3	P1C2D3B3A1 8Stéphanie

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Dependent Variable		
2	1	1	1	P2C1D1B1A1 9Colette		
			2	P2C1D1B2A2 0Josette		
			3	P2C1D1B3A2 1Liliane		
		2	2	1	P2C1D2B1A2 2Eliane	
				2	P2C1D2B2A2 3Jeannine	
				3	P2C1D2B3A2 4Yvette	
		3	3	1	P2C1D3B1A2 5Gisèle	
				2	P2C1D3B2A2 6Denise	
				3	P2C1D3B3A2 7Francine	
	2	1	1	1	P2C2D1B1A2 8Thérèse	
				2	P2C2D1B2A2 9Ghislaine	
				3	P2C2D1B3A3 0Delphine	
			2	2	1	P2C2D2B1A3 1Céline
					2	P2C2D2B2A3 2Cécile
					3	P2C2D2B3A3 3Sabine
3			3	1	P2C2D3B1A3 4Sandra	
				2	P2C2D3B2A3 5Laure	
				3	P2C2D3B3A3 6Claire	

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
P1C1D1B1 A 1 Dominique	8,78	2,083	132
P1C1D1B2 A 2 Elisabeth	6,05	3,058	132
P1C1D1B3 A 3 Magali	3,39	3,149	132
P1C1D2B1 A 4 Michèle	8,52	2,310	132
P1C1D2B2 A 5 Jocelyne	5,83	3,130	132
P1C1D2B3 A6 Agnès	3,47	2,997	132
P1C1D3B1 A 7 Christiane	8,43	2,339	132
P1C1D3B2 A 8 Maryse	6,22	3,055	132
P1C1D3B3 A 9 Anne-Marie	4,50	3,606	132
P1C2D1B1 A 10 Jacqueline	9,17	1,687	132
P1C2D1B2 A 11 Danielle	7,29	2,694	132
P1C2D1B3 A 12 Sylviane	5,91	3,095	132
P1C2D2B1 A 13 Geneviève	9,03	1,824	132
P1C2D2B2 A 14 Valérie	7,01	2,891	132
P1C2D2B3 A15 Sandrine	5,46	3,218	132
P1C2D3B1 A 16 Christelle	8,84	1,885	132
P1C2D3B2 A 17 Carole	6,89	3,168	132
P1C2D3B3 A 18 Stéphanie	6,31	3,167	132
P2C1D1B1 A 19 Colette	7,87	2,365	132
P2C1D1B2 A 20 Josette	5,36	3,136	132
P2C1D1B3 A21 Liliane	3,08	3,249	132
P2C1D2B1 A 22 Eliane	7,82	2,350	132
P2C1D2B2 A 23 Jeannine	5,42	3,092	132
P2C1D2B3 A 24 Yvette	2,89	2,971	132
P2C1D3B1 A 25 Gisèle	7,72	2,524	132
P2C1D3B2 A 26 Denise	5,49	3,478	132
P2C1D3B3 A27 Francine	4,29	3,714	132
P2C2D1B1 A 28 Thérèse	8,24	2,126	132
P2C2D1B2 A 29 Ghislaine	6,40	2,852	132
P2C2D1B3 A 30 Delphine	4,93	3,220	132
P2C2D2B1 A 31 Céline	8,15	2,088	132

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
P2C2D2B2 A 32 Cécile	6,36	2,837	132
P2C2D2B3 A 33 Sabine	4,75	3,328	132
P2C2D3B1 A 34 Sandra	8,12	2,305	132
P2C2D3B2 A 35 Laure	6,45	3,015	132
P2C2D3B3 A 36 Claire	5,49	3,474	132

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,357	72,847 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,643	72,847 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,556	72,847 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,556	72,847 ^b	1,000	131,000
Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,467	114,990 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,533	114,990 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,878	114,990 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,878	114,990 ^b	1,000	131,000
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,098	7,039 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,902	7,039 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,108	7,039 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,108	7,039 ^b	2,000	130,000
Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,728	173,564 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,272	173,564 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	2,670	173,564 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	2,670	173,564 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,045	6,161 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,955	6,161 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,047	6,161 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,047	6,161 ^b	1,000	131,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,033	2,209 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,967	2,209 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,034	2,209 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,034	2,209 ^b	2,000	130,000
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,045	3,097 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,955	3,097 ^b	2,000	130,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,000	,357
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,357
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,357
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,357
Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,000	,467
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,467
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,467
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,467
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,001	,098
	Wilks' Lambda	,001	,098
	Hotelling's Trace	,001	,098
	Roy's Largest Root	,001	,098
Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,728
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,728
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,728
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,728
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,014	,045
	Wilks' Lambda	,014	,045
	Hotelling's Trace	,014	,045
	Roy's Largest Root	,014	,045
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,114	,033
	Wilks' Lambda	,114	,033
	Hotelling's Trace	,114	,033
	Roy's Largest Root	,114	,033
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,049	,045
	Wilks' Lambda	,049	,045

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
	Hotelling's Trace	,048	3,097 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,048	3,097 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,006	,402 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,994	,402 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,006	,402 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,006	,402 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,032	2,137 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,968	2,137 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,033	2,137 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,033	2,137 ^b	2,000	130,000
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,313	29,547 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,687	29,547 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,455	29,547 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,455	29,547 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,036	2,408 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,964	2,408 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,037	2,408 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,037	2,408 ^b	2,000	130,000
Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,202	8,102 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,798	8,102 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,253	8,102 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,253	8,102 ^b	4,000	128,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,009	,297 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,991	,297 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,009	,297 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,009	,297 ^b	4,000	128,000
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,067	2,316 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,933	2,316 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,072	2,316 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,072	2,316 ^b	4,000	128,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,042	1,399 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,958	1,399 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,044	1,399 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,044	1,399 ^b	4,000	128,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
	Hotelling's Trace	,049	,045
	Roy's Largest Root	,049	,045
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,670	,006
	Wilks' Lambda	,670	,006
	Hotelling's Trace	,670	,006
	Roy's Largest Root	,670	,006
Physical.activity * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,122	,032
	Wilks' Lambda	,122	,032
	Hotelling's Trace	,122	,032
	Roy's Largest Root	,122	,032
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,313
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,313
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,313
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,313
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,094	,036
	Wilks' Lambda	,094	,036
	Hotelling's Trace	,094	,036
	Roy's Largest Root	,094	,036
Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,202
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,202
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,202
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,202
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,880	,009
	Wilks' Lambda	,880	,009
	Hotelling's Trace	,880	,009
	Roy's Largest Root	,880	,009
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,061	,067
	Wilks' Lambda	,061	,067
	Hotelling's Trace	,061	,067
	Roy's Largest Root	,061	,067
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,238	,042
	Wilks' Lambda	,238	,042
	Hotelling's Trace	,238	,042
	Roy's Largest Root	,238	,042

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Drinking.habits + Diagnosis + Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior + Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

b. Exact statistic

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Epsilon ^b Greenhouse-Geisser
Physical.activity	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Drinking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Diagnosis	,433	108,758	2	,000	,638
Behavior	,877	17,064	2	,000	,890
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,841	22,586	2	,000	,862
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,914	11,696	2	,003	,921
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,963	4,903	2	,086	,964
Physical.activity * Behavior	,945	7,291	2	,026	,948
Drinking.habits * Behavior	,862	19,340	2	,000	,879
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	,958	5,602	2	,061	,960
Diagnosis * Behavior	,511	86,987	9	,000	,740
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	,831	23,933	9	,004	,903
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,809	27,420	9	,001	,908
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,925	10,091	9	,343	,964

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Epsilon ^b	
	Huynh-Feldt	Lower-bound
Physical.activity	1,000	1,000
Drinking.habits	1,000	1,000
Diagnosis	,642	,500
Behavior	,902	,500
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	1,000	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,873	,500
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,933	,500
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,978	,500
Physical.activity * Behavior	,962	,500
Drinking.habits * Behavior	,890	,500
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	,973	,500
Diagnosis * Behavior	,759	,250
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	,932	,250
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,938	,250
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,997	,250

Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.

-

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Drinking.habits + Diagnosis + Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior + Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

b. May be used to adjust the degrees of freedom for the averaged tests of significance. Corrected tests are displayed in the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table.

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	550,910	1	550,910
	Greenhouse-Geisser	550,910	1,000	550,910
	Huynh-Feldt	550,910	1,000	550,910
	Lower-bound	550,910	1,000	550,910
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed	990,701	131	7,563
	Greenhouse-Geisser	990,701	131,000	7,563
	Huynh-Feldt	990,701	131,000	7,563
	Lower-bound	990,701	131,000	7,563
Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	1420,371	1	1420,371
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1420,371	1,000	1420,371
	Huynh-Feldt	1420,371	1,000	1420,371
	Lower-bound	1420,371	1,000	1420,371
Error(Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	1618,129	131	12,352
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1618,129	131,000	12,352
	Huynh-Feldt	1618,129	131,000	12,352
	Lower-bound	1618,129	131,000	12,352
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	90,821	2	45,411
	Greenhouse-Geisser	90,821	1,276	71,150
	Huynh-Feldt	90,821	1,283	70,763
	Lower-bound	90,821	1,000	90,821
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	1836,290	262	7,009
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1836,290	167,218	10,981
	Huynh-Feldt	1836,290	168,133	10,922
	Lower-bound	1836,290	131,000	14,017
Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	11811,214	2	5905,607
	Greenhouse-Geisser	11811,214	1,781	6632,064
	Huynh-Feldt	11811,214	1,804	6548,051
	Lower-bound	11811,214	1,000	11811,214
Error(Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	6567,064	262	25,065
	Greenhouse-Geisser	6567,064	233,301	28,148
	Huynh-Feldt	6567,064	236,295	27,792
	Lower-bound	6567,064	131,000	50,130
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	11,721	1	11,721
	Greenhouse-Geisser	11,721	1,000	11,721
	Huynh-Feldt	11,721	1,000	11,721
	Lower-bound	11,721	1,000	11,721

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	72,847	,000	,357
	Greenhouse-Geisser	72,847	,000	,357
	Huynh-Feldt	72,847	,000	,357
	Lower-bound	72,847	,000	,357
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	114,990	,000	,467
	Greenhouse-Geisser	114,990	,000	,467
	Huynh-Feldt	114,990	,000	,467
	Lower-bound	114,990	,000	,467
Error(Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	6,479	,002	,047
	Greenhouse-Geisser	6,479	,007	,047
	Huynh-Feldt	6,479	,007	,047
	Lower-bound	6,479	,012	,047
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	235,610	,000	,643
	Greenhouse-Geisser	235,610	,000	,643
	Huynh-Feldt	235,610	,000	,643
	Lower-bound	235,610	,000	,643
Error(Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	6,161	,014	,045
	Greenhouse-Geisser	6,161	,014	,045
	Huynh-Feldt	6,161	,014	,045
	Lower-bound	6,161	,014	,045

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	249,224	131	1,902
	Greenhouse-Geisser	249,224	131,000	1,902
	Huynh-Feldt	249,224	131,000	1,902
	Lower-bound	249,224	131,000	1,902
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	6,748	2	3,374
	Greenhouse-Geisser	6,748	1,725	3,912
	Huynh-Feldt	6,748	1,746	3,865
	Lower-bound	6,748	1,000	6,748
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	497,808	262	1,900
	Greenhouse-Geisser	497,808	225,963	2,203
	Huynh-Feldt	497,808	228,699	2,177
	Lower-bound	497,808	131,000	3,800
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	22,206	2	11,103
	Greenhouse-Geisser	22,206	1,842	12,058
	Huynh-Feldt	22,206	1,867	11,897
	Lower-bound	22,206	1,000	22,206
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	721,461	262	2,754
	Greenhouse-Geisser	721,461	241,243	2,991
	Huynh-Feldt	721,461	244,522	2,950
	Lower-bound	721,461	131,000	5,507
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	1,695	2	,847
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,695	1,929	,879
	Huynh-Feldt	1,695	1,957	,866
	Lower-bound	1,695	1,000	1,695
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	459,194	262	1,753
	Greenhouse-Geisser	459,194	252,649	1,818
	Huynh-Feldt	459,194	256,352	1,791
	Lower-bound	459,194	131,000	3,505
Physical.activity * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	9,810	2	4,905
	Greenhouse-Geisser	9,810	1,897	5,172
	Huynh-Feldt	9,810	1,924	5,100
	Lower-bound	9,810	1,000	9,810
Error(Physical. activity*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	702,246	262	2,680
	Greenhouse-Geisser	702,246	248,450	2,827
	Huynh-Feldt	702,246	251,995	2,787
	Lower-bound	702,246	131,000	5,361

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	1,776	,171	,013
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,776	,177	,013
	Huynh-Feldt	1,776	,176	,013
	Lower-bound	1,776	,185	,013
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	4,032	,019	,030
	Greenhouse-Geisser	4,032	,022	,030
	Huynh-Feldt	4,032	,021	,030
	Lower-bound	4,032	,047	,030
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	,484	,617	,004
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,484	,610	,004
	Huynh-Feldt	,484	,613	,004
	Lower-bound	,484	,488	,004
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1,830	,162	,014
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,830	,165	,014
	Huynh-Feldt	1,830	,164	,014
	Lower-bound	1,830	,178	,014
Error(Physical. activity*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	432,591	2	216,295
	Greenhouse-Geisser	432,591	1,757	246,194
	Huynh-Feldt	432,591	1,779	243,149
	Lower-bound	432,591	1,000	432,591
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	1482,576	262	5,659
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1482,576	230,182	6,441
	Huynh-Feldt	1482,576	233,065	6,361
	Lower-bound	1482,576	131,000	11,317
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	10,921	2	5,460
	Greenhouse-Geisser	10,921	1,919	5,691
	Huynh-Feldt	10,921	1,947	5,609
	Lower-bound	10,921	1,000	10,921
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	555,135	262	2,119
	Greenhouse-Geisser	555,135	251,398	2,208
	Huynh-Feldt	555,135	255,053	2,177
	Lower-bound	555,135	131,000	4,238
Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	231,227	4	57,807
	Greenhouse-Geisser	231,227	2,959	78,142
	Huynh-Feldt	231,227	3,035	76,188
	Lower-bound	231,227	1,000	231,227
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	2051,829	524	3,916
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2051,829	387,637	5,293
	Huynh-Feldt	2051,829	397,576	5,161
	Lower-bound	2051,829	131,000	15,663
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	2,495	4	,624
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,495	3,614	,690
	Huynh-Feldt	2,495	3,729	,669
	Lower-bound	2,495	1,000	2,495
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	1085,783	524	2,072
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1085,783	473,384	2,294
	Huynh-Feldt	1085,783	488,472	2,223
	Lower-bound	1085,783	131,000	8,288
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	16,521	4	4,130
	Greenhouse-Geisser	16,521	3,634	4,547
	Huynh-Feldt	16,521	3,750	4,405
	Lower-bound	16,521	1,000	16,521

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	38,224	,000	,226
	Greenhouse-Geisser	38,224	,000	,226
	Huynh-Feldt	38,224	,000	,226
	Lower-bound	38,224	,000	,226
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	2,577	,078	,019
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,577	,080	,019
	Huynh-Feldt	2,577	,079	,019
	Lower-bound	2,577	,111	,019
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	14,763	,000	,101
	Greenhouse-Geisser	14,763	,000	,101
	Huynh-Feldt	14,763	,000	,101
	Lower-bound	14,763	,000	,101
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	,301	,877	,002
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,301	,860	,002
	Huynh-Feldt	,301	,865	,002
	Lower-bound	,301	,584	,002
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1,739	,140	,013
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,739	,147	,013
	Huynh-Feldt	1,739	,144	,013
	Lower-bound	1,739	,190	,013

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	1244,645	524	2,375
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1244,645	476,023	2,615
	Huynh-Feldt	1244,645	491,285	2,533
	Lower-bound	1244,645	131,000	9,501
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	10,111	4	2,528
	Greenhouse-Geisser	10,111	3,855	2,623
	Huynh-Feldt	10,111	3,987	2,536
	Lower-bound	10,111	1,000	10,111
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	974,500	524	1,860
	Greenhouse-Geisser	974,500	505,009	1,930
	Huynh-Feldt	974,500	522,232	1,866
	Lower-bound	974,500	131,000	7,439

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1,359	,247	,010
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,359	,248	,010
	Huynh-Feldt	1,359	,247	,010
	Lower-bound	1,359	,246	,010
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior
Physical.activity	Linear			
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear			
Drinking.habits		Linear		
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear		
Diagnosis			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Behavior				Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Behavior)				Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear		
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear		
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity	Linear				550,910
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				990,701
Drinking.habits		Linear			1420,371
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			1618,129
Diagnosis			Linear		28,599
			Quadratic		62,222
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		1199,026
			Quadratic		637,264
Behavior				Linear	11753,284
				Quadratic	57,930
Error(Behavior)				Linear	4402,216
				Quadratic	2164,848
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			11,721
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			249,224
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		6,276
			Quadratic		,472
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		287,683
			Quadratic		210,125
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		21,175
			Quadratic		1,031
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		459,784
			Quadratic		261,677
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,682
			Quadratic		,013
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		273,276
			Quadratic		185,918
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	8,490
				Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	371,177
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	427,682
				Quadratic	
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	952,152
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	df
Physical.activity	Linear				1
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				131
Drinking.habits		Linear			1
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			131
Diagnosis			Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Behavior				Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Behavior)				Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			131
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	131
				Quadratic	131

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Linear				550,910
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				7,563
Drinking.habits		Linear			1420,371
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			12,352
Diagnosis			Linear		28,599
			Quadratic		62,222
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		9,153
			Quadratic		4,865
Behavior				Linear	11753,284
				Quadratic	57,930
Error(Behavior)				Linear	33,605
				Quadratic	16,526
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			11,721
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			1,902
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		6,276
			Quadratic		,472
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		2,196
			Quadratic		1,604
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		21,175
			Quadratic		1,031
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		3,510
			Quadratic		1,998
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,682
			Quadratic		,013
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		2,086
			Quadratic		1,419
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	8,490
				Quadratic	1,320
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	2,833
				Quadratic	2,527
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	427,682
				Quadratic	4,909
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	7,268
				Quadratic	4,049

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	F
Physical.activity	Linear				72,847
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Drinking.habits		Linear			114,990
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		3,125
			Quadratic		12,791
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	349,751
				Quadratic	3,505
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			6,161
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		2,858
			Quadratic		,294
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		6,033
			Quadratic		,516
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,806
			Quadratic		,009
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	2,996
				Quadratic	,522
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	58,842
				Quadratic	1,212
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Sig.
Physical.activity	Linear				,000
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Drinking.habits		Linear			,000
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,079
			Quadratic		,000
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,063
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			,014
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,093
			Quadratic		,588
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,015
			Quadratic		,474
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,371
			Quadratic		,925
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	,086
				Quadratic	,471
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,273
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Linear				,357
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Drinking.habits		Linear			,467
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,023
			Quadratic		,089
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	,728
				Quadratic	,026
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			,045
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,021
			Quadratic		,002
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,044
			Quadratic		,004
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,006
			Quadratic		,000
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	,022
				Quadratic	,004
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	,310
				Quadratic	,009
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	7,880
				Quadratic	3,041
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	244,787
				Quadratic	310,348
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	148,485
				Quadratic	16,364
			Quadratic	Linear	57,960
				Quadratic	8,418
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	778,515
				Quadratic	521,136
			Quadratic	Linear	482,790
				Quadratic	269,388
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,189
				Quadratic	,051
			Quadratic	Linear	,395
				Quadratic	1,859
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	270,561
				Quadratic	277,866
			Quadratic	Linear	226,939
				Quadratic	310,418
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	16,381
				Quadratic	,003
			Quadratic	Linear	,091
				Quadratic	,047
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	257,619
				Quadratic	378,164
			Quadratic	Linear	246,826
				Quadratic	362,036
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,017
				Quadratic	2,124
			Quadratic	Linear	4,889
				Quadratic	3,081
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	285,233
				Quadratic	269,293
			Quadratic	Linear	196,444
				Quadratic	223,530

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	df
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean Square
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	7,880
				Quadratic	3,041
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	1,869
				Quadratic	2,369
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	148,485
				Quadratic	16,364
			Quadratic	Linear	57,960
				Quadratic	8,418
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	5,943
				Quadratic	3,978
			Quadratic	Linear	3,685
				Quadratic	2,056
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,189
				Quadratic	,051
			Quadratic	Linear	,395
				Quadratic	1,859
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	2,065
				Quadratic	2,121
			Quadratic	Linear	1,732
				Quadratic	2,370
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	16,381
				Quadratic	,003
			Quadratic	Linear	,091
				Quadratic	,047
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	1,967
				Quadratic	2,887
			Quadratic	Linear	1,884
				Quadratic	2,764
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,017
				Quadratic	2,124
			Quadratic	Linear	4,889
				Quadratic	3,081
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	2,177
				Quadratic	2,056
			Quadratic	Linear	1,500
				Quadratic	1,706

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	F
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	4,217
				Quadratic	1,284
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	24,985
				Quadratic	4,114
			Quadratic	Linear	15,727
				Quadratic	4,093
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,092
				Quadratic	,024
			Quadratic	Linear	,228
				Quadratic	,785
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	8,330
				Quadratic	,001
			Quadratic	Linear	,048
				Quadratic	,017
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,008
				Quadratic	1,033
			Quadratic	Linear	3,260
				Quadratic	1,806
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Sig.
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,042
				Quadratic	,259
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,045
			Quadratic	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,045
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,763
				Quadratic	,877
			Quadratic	Linear	,634
				Quadratic	,377
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	,005
				Quadratic	,976
			Quadratic	Linear	,826
				Quadratic	,896
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,930
				Quadratic	,311
			Quadratic	Linear	,073
				Quadratic	,181
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,031
				Quadratic	,010
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	,160
				Quadratic	,030
			Quadratic	Linear	,107
				Quadratic	,030
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,001
				Quadratic	,000
			Quadratic	Linear	,002
				Quadratic	,006
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	,060
				Quadratic	,000
			Quadratic	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,000
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,008
			Quadratic	Linear	,024
				Quadratic	,014
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	193864,458	1	193864,458	1431,452	,000	,916
Error	17741,598	131	135,432			

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Grand Mean

Measure: MEASURE_1

Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
6,387	,169	6,053	6,721

2. Physical.activity

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,728	,165	6,402	7,054
2	6,047	,182	5,687	6,406

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	,681 [*]	,080	,000	,523
2	1	-,681 [*]	,080	,000	-,839

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	,839
2	1	-,523

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,357	72,847 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,357
Wilks' lambda	,643	72,847 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,357
Hotelling's trace	,556	72,847 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,357
Roy's largest root	,556	72,847 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,357

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Physical.activity. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

3. Drinking.habits

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	5,840	,183	5,478	6,203
2	6,934	,169	6,599	7,269

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Drinking.habits	(J) Drinking.habits	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence
					Lower Bound
1	2	-1,093*	,102	,000	-1,295
2	1	1,093*	,102	,000	,892

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Drinking.habits	(J) Drinking.habits	95% Confidence
		Interval for ^b ...
1	2	Upper Bound -,892
2	1	Upper Bound 1,295

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,467	114,990 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,467
Wilks' lambda	,533	114,990 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,467
Hotelling's trace	,878	114,990 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,467
Roy's largest root	,878	114,990 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,467

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Drinking.habits. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

4. Diagnosis

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,373	,165	6,047	6,699
2	6,225	,172	5,886	6,565
3	6,563	,194	6,178	6,948

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	,148 [*]	,047	,002	,054
	3	-,190	,108	,079	-,403
2	1	-,148 [*]	,047	,002	-,241
	3	-,338 [*]	,113	,003	-,561
3	1	,190	,108	,079	-,023
	2	,338 [*]	,113	,003	,114

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	95% Confidence Interval for ^b ..
		Upper Bound
1	2	,241
	3	,023
2	1	-,054
	3	-,114
3	1	,403
	2	,561

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,098	7,039 ^a	2,000	130,000	,001	,098
Wilks' lambda	,902	7,039 ^a	2,000	130,000	,001	,098
Hotelling's trace	,108	7,039 ^a	2,000	130,000	,001	,098
Roy's largest root	,108	7,039 ^a	2,000	130,000	,001	,098

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Diagnosis. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

5. Behavior

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	8,391	,143	8,108	8,675
2	6,231	,213	5,809	6,653
3	4,539	,226	4,092	4,986

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Behavior	(J) Behavior	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	2,160*	,169	,000	1,826	2,495
	3	3,852*	,206	,000	3,445	4,260
2	1	-2,160*	,169	,000	-2,495	-1,826
	3	1,692*	,155	,000	1,386	1,998
3	1	-3,852*	,206	,000	-4,260	-3,445
	2	-1,692*	,155	,000	-1,998	-1,386

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,728	173,564 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,728
Wilks' lambda	,272	173,564 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,728
Hotelling's trace	2,670	173,564 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,728
Roy's largest root	2,670	173,564 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,728

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Behavior. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

6. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,131	,181	5,773	6,490
	2	7,324	,167	6,994	7,654
2	1	5,550	,194	5,165	5,934
	2	6,544	,184	6,179	6,908

7. Physical.activity * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,765	,162	6,445	7,085
	2	6,552	,171	6,213	6,890
	3	6,866	,188	6,495	7,237
2	1	5,981	,183	5,620	6,343
	2	5,899	,184	5,534	6,263
	3	6,260	,212	5,840	6,680

8. Physical.activity * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,795	,144	8,511	9,080
	2	6,548	,220	6,112	6,984
	3	4,840	,224	4,397	5,283
2	1	7,987	,163	7,665	8,310
	2	5,914	,219	5,480	6,348
	3	4,239	,238	3,768	4,710

9. Drinking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	5,755	,184	5,390	6,120
	2	5,658	,183	5,296	6,019
	3	6,109	,216	5,682	6,535
2	1	6,991	,171	6,654	7,329
	2	6,793	,178	6,440	7,146
	3	7,018	,191	6,640	7,395

10. Drinking.habits * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,189	,169	7,855	8,524
	2	5,730	,233	5,269	6,191
	3	3,602	,243	3,121	4,083
2	1	8,593	,135	8,325	8,861
	2	6,732	,217	6,302	7,162
	3	5,476	,238	5,005	5,947

11. Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,517	,140	8,239	8,795
	2	6,277	,215	5,852	6,701
	3	4,326	,233	3,865	4,787
2	1	8,379	,154	8,073	8,684
	2	6,153	,223	5,713	6,594
	3	4,144	,240	3,670	4,618
3	1	8,278	,161	7,960	8,596
	2	6,263	,242	5,785	6,741
	3	5,148	,269	4,615	5,680

12. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
1	1	1	6,073	,185	5,707
		2	5,937	,185	5,571
		3	6,384	,210	5,969
	2	1	7,457	,170	7,120
		2	7,167	,181	6,808
		3	7,348	,188	6,976
2	1	1	5,437	,204	5,034
		2	5,379	,196	4,992
		3	5,833	,236	5,366
	2	1	6,525	,193	6,143
		2	6,419	,193	6,038
		3	6,687	,212	6,267

12. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	95% Confidence .
			Upper Bound
1	1	1	6,440
		2	6,303
		3	6,799
	2	1	7,794
		2	7,525
		3	7,721
2	1	1	5,840
		2	5,766
		3	6,300
	2	1	6,908
		2	6,801
		3	7,107

13. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	8,576	,177	8,226	8,926
		2	6,033	,243	5,551	6,514
		3	3,785	,249	3,294	4,277
	2	1	9,015	,136	8,746	9,284
		2	7,063	,228	6,612	7,514
		3	5,894	,238	5,424	6,364
2	1	1	7,803	,182	7,444	8,162
		2	5,427	,243	4,947	5,907
		3	3,419	,254	2,916	3,922
	2	1	8,172	,165	7,844	8,499
		2	6,402	,223	5,961	6,842
		3	5,058	,252	4,559	5,557

14. Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	8,977	,144	8,692	9,263
		2	6,670	,222	6,231	7,109
		3	4,648	,237	4,179	5,116
	2	1	8,773	,160	8,455	9,090
		2	6,417	,238	5,946	6,887
		3	4,466	,245	3,980	4,952
	3	1	8,636	,161	8,317	8,955
		2	6,557	,245	6,072	7,042
		3	5,405	,270	4,872	5,939
2	1	1	8,057	,169	7,723	8,391
		2	5,883	,233	5,422	6,343
		3	4,004	,251	3,507	4,501
	2	1	7,985	,177	7,635	8,335
		2	5,890	,236	5,423	6,358
		3	3,822	,250	3,327	4,317
	3	1	7,920	,188	7,548	8,293
		2	5,970	,260	5,456	6,483
		3	4,890	,290	4,316	5,464

15. Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	8,326	,174	7,982	8,669
		2	5,708	,251	5,212	6,204
		3	3,231	,257	2,723	3,739
	2	1	8,167	,184	7,803	8,531
		2	5,625	,247	5,135	6,115
		3	3,182	,246	2,694	3,669
	3	1	8,076	,195	7,689	8,462
		2	5,856	,265	5,333	6,379
		3	4,394	,300	3,800	4,988
2	1	1	8,708	,143	8,426	8,991
		2	6,845	,223	6,403	7,286
		3	5,420	,257	4,912	5,929
	2	1	8,591	,148	8,299	8,883
		2	6,682	,231	6,225	7,138
		3	5,106	,272	4,569	5,643
	3	1	8,481	,156	8,172	8,790
		2	6,670	,256	6,165	7,176
		3	5,902	,272	5,364	6,439

16. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% ... Lower Bound	
1	1	1	1	8,780	,181	8,422	
			2	6,053	,266	5,527	
			3	3,386	,274	2,844	
		2	1	8,515	,201	8,117	
			2	5,826	,272	5,287	
			3	3,470	,261	2,954	
		3	1	8,432	,204	8,029	
			2	6,220	,266	5,694	
			3	4,500	,314	3,879	
	2	1	1	1	9,174	,147	8,884
				2	7,288	,235	6,824
				3	5,909	,269	5,376
			2	1	9,030	,159	8,716
				2	7,008	,252	6,510
				3	5,462	,280	4,908
3		1	8,841	,164	8,516		
		2	6,894	,276	6,349		
		3	6,311	,276	5,765		
2	1	1	1	7,871	,206	7,464	
			2	5,364	,273	4,824	
			3	3,076	,283	2,516	
		2	1	7,818	,205	7,413	
			2	5,424	,269	4,892	
			3	2,894	,259	2,382	
		3	1	7,720	,220	7,285	
			2	5,492	,303	4,894	
			3	4,288	,323	3,648	
	2	1	1	8,242	,185	7,876	
			2	6,402	,248	5,910	
			3	4,932	,280	4,377	
		2	1	8,152	,182	7,792	
			2	6,356	,247	5,868	
			3	4,750	,290	4,177	
3	1	8,121	,201	7,724			
	2	6,447	,262	5,928			
	3	5,492	,302	4,894			

16. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

				95% Confidence .	
Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Upper Bound	
1	1	1	1	9,139	
			2	6,579	
			3	3,929	
		2	1	8,913	
			2	6,365	
			3	3,986	
		3	1	8,834	
			2	6,746	
			3	5,121	
	2	1	1	1	9,465
				2	7,752
				3	6,442
			2	1	9,344
				2	7,505
				3	6,016
3		1	9,166		
		2	7,439		
		3	6,856		
2	1	1	1	8,278	
			2	5,904	
			3	3,635	
		2	1	8,223	
			2	5,957	
			3	3,406	
		3	1	8,154	
			2	6,091	
			3	4,927	
	2	1	1	1	8,609
				2	6,893
				3	5,486
			2	1	8,511
				2	6,845
				3	5,323
3	1	8,518			
	2	6,966			
	3	6,091			